

PROJECT HIGHLIGHTS

The PREFER project was a joint undertaking by 33 public and private partners with over 130 people representing academic institutions, pharmaceutical companies, health technology agencies, and patient organisations in European countries and in the US working to provide recommendations on why, when and how to assess and use patient preferences in medical product decision.

Patient preference information includes the relative importance of what matters most to patients, as well as the trade-offs that patients are willing to make between treatment characteristics, or other attributes of treatments or health interventions.

PREFER recommendations

The PREFER recommendations provide scientifically based insights from six years of research on when and how to design and conduct a patient preference study:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6470922>

A brief version of the PREFER recommendations with the key message can be found here:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6470918>

EMA qualification opinion

A positive qualification opinion was provided by EMA (CHMP) on the Framework and Points to Consider for Methods Selection:

https://www.ema.europa.eu/documents/regulatory-procedural-guideline/qualification-opinion-imi-prefer_en.pdf

Templates

A set of 11 templates for patient preference studies were set up by the project and are freely available here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6400552>

Training

16 webinars have been recorded for training purposes. For most recordings, the links to the slides can be found in the description of the videos. Watch them here:

https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLN-kgkHBHa25apivf7wlwqNv5HiVX_VCZ or

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6397608>

PREFER conducted 11 case studies: <https://imi-prefer.eu/case-studies/>
More than 40 papers have been published: <https://imi-prefer.eu/publications/>
All other material can be found here: <https://zenodo.org/communities/prefer/>
General slide deck: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6592357>